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Data management plan (DMP)

X-ray experiments and practical applications

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	30/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Absorption thickness	Raw data, Plain text, Configuration data	.txt and .labx	<100 MB	no
P2	Lab report	Other	PDF document	<100 MB	no
P3	Absorption material	Raw data, Plain text, Configuration data	.txt and .labx	<100 MB	no
P4	Bragg-reflexion	Raw data, Plain text, Configuration data	.txt and .labx	<100 MB	no
P5	Duane-Hunt law	Raw data, Plain text, Configuration data	.txt and .labx	<100 MB	no

Description for "Absorption thickness":

Raw data and metadata of the experiment 'Absorption based on thickness'. Files provided by software as .labx (software specific) and .txt files.

Description for "Lab report":

Latex written lap report, analysing produced data and reused data, combining the information gathered.

Description for "Absorption material":

Raw data and metadata of the experiment 'Absorption based on material'. Files provided by software as .labx (software specific) and .txt files.

Description for "Bragg-Reflexion":

Raw data and metadata of the experiment 'Bragg-Reflexion'. Files provided by software as .labx (software specific) and .txt files.

Description for "Duane-Hunt law":

Raw data and metadata of the experiment 'Duane-Hunt law and planck constant'. Files provided by software as .labx (software specific) and .txt files.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Raw Data: Magnetostrictive FeCoSiB coated ZnO Microstructures by Bragg Coherent X-Ray Diffraction Imaging	Zenodo	CC-BY-4.0	no
R2	X-Ray Database	re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories	Upon request*(see description)	no
R3	Uric acid detection in visible spectrum	TELKOMNIKA Telecommunication, Computing, Electronics and Control	CC-BY-SA-4.0	no
R4	Duane -- Hunt relation improved	arXiv.org	arXiv.org perpetual, non-exclusive license 1.0	no

Description for "Raw Data: Magnetostrictive FeCoSiB coated ZnO Microstructures by Bragg Coherent X-Ray Diffraction Imaging":

Five sets of raw data from (Fe₉₀Co₁₀)₇₈Si₁₂B₁₀ coated ZnO microstructure (rod) investigated by Bragg coherent X-ray diffraction imaging. FeCoSiB is a magnetostrictive alloy, thus a changing strain is expected for applied magnetic fields. Included is data from the same spatial positions along the c-axis of the ZnO rod at five different magnetic flux densities [0, 4.4, 5.6, 9.1, 13.2]/mT. Further on called P1 to P5. For each position there is a .nxs file of a rocking scan around the {0001} Bragg reflection, collected by a 2D detector and other recorded values, e.g. motor positions, counter values.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8338903>

Description for "X-Ray Database":

The primary interaction of low-energy x rays within matter, viz. photoabsorption and coherent scattering, have been described for photon energies outside the absorption threshold regions. These tables are based on a compilation of the available experimental measurements and theoretical calculations. For many elements there is little or no published data and in such cases it was necessary to rely on theoretical calculations and interpolations across Z. In order to improve the accuracy in the future considerably more experimental measurements are needed.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17616/R34K5S> last accessed: 2025-10-30

*The Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, provider of this dataset, does not provide a standardised copyright licence like CC-BY-4.0. Instead, they provide a licence and the right to use the

dataset upon request as described on their main website: <https://www.lbl.gov/terms-and-conditions/>.

Description for "Duane -- Hunt relation improved":

In present paper the Duane-Hunt relation for direct measurement of the Planck constant is improved by including of relativistic corrections. New relation to determine the Planck constant, suggested in this paper contains Duane-Hunt relation as first term and can be applied in a wide range of energies. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1506.08783>

Description for "Uric acid detection in visible spectrum":

The measurement of uric acid based on the optical absorption at visible light spectrum is investigated and tested. Sensing in the visible region was conducted for determination of suitable wavelength that produces high sensitivity and accuracy performance based on the Beer-Lambert law calculation. In this work, the uric acid is detected by detecting sodium urate as a product of chemical reaction between uric acid with sodium hydroxide buffer. The setup has been tested for uric acid concentration ranging from 15 mg/dL to 85 mg/dL. Three wavelengths have been analysed which are 460 nm, 525 nm and 630 nm. Measured data at 460nm wavelength exhibits the highest sensitivity, which is 0.0012 (mg/dL)-with 86.51% accuracy. Detection of uric acid at visible light spectrum offers a low-cost sensor based on visible LEDs and photodiode is possible to be realized. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.12928/TELKOMNIKA.v18i4.14993>

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Experiments with a 'Röntgengrundgerät' and necessary samples by the company 'LD Didactic' will be performed. The data from the tool will be evaluated via the corresponding software 'CASSY LAB 2', provided by a PC in the lab by the TU Wien. The data will stay at the TU on the PC in the lab. All the equipment used is provided by the TU Wien. Furthermore, existing datasets will be reused to follow up the performed experiments and combine the findings with practical applications. Three of the reused datasets are available under CC-BY or CC-BY-SA licenses, and one provided the right to use it upon request.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in the README file. Due to the short project length, there is no versioning intended.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level and to explain software specific file-types. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Experiment descriptions and parameters, as well as findings and analysis of the produced data will be described in a written report of the experiments as part of the dataset and uploaded as well.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: Peer review of the data and control sets of data for each experiment, provided by the project organiser, which were compared with the produced data to ensure accuracy.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Sylvia Hogen (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (Absorption thickness), P2 (Lab report), P3 (Absorption material), P4 (Bragg-reflexion), P5 (Duane-Hunt law), R1 (Raw Data: Magnetostrictive FeCoSiB coated ZnO Microstructures by Bragg Coherent X-Ray Diffraction Imaging), R2 (X-Ray Database), R3 (Uric acid detection in visible spectrum), R4 (Duane -- Hunt relation improved) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by Campus IT. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
P2	writing	reading only	no access
P3	writing	reading only	no access
P4	writing	reading only	no access
P5	writing	reading only	no access
R1	reading only	reading only	no access
R2	reading only	reading only	no access
R3	reading only	reading only	no access
R4	reading only	reading only	no access

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individuals hold rights and control access to the project data: The project members as well as the project organisers will have access rights and control access to all the datasets, produced and reused.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P5	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The datasets may best be used with the software used during the research, 'CASSY LAB 2'. As the files will be exported as .txt files as well, other means to analyse the data are possible, without the need for any specific software.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Potential users may be students conducting similar experiments to use as reference work and researchers working on topics expanding on the contents/data.
sP2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P4	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P5	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The contact Person Sylvia Hogen will direct the data management process overall, with the project members responsible for ensuring metadata production and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.